

Microwave assisted one pot green synthesis of novel isoxazoline derivatives using *N*-methyl- α -chloro nitron and their antibacterial activities

Bhaskar Chakraborty^{a*}, Prawin Kumar Sharma^a and Amalesh Samanta^b

^aOrganic Chemistry Laboratory, Sikkim Government College, Gangtok-737 102, Sikkim, India

E-mail : bcorgchem@hotmail.com

^bDivision of Microbiology, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

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Abstract : Microwave assisted 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction of *N*-methyl- α -chloro nitron with various alkynes as dipolarophile have been studied and found to afford diastereomeric novel isoxazoline derivatives with high selectivity. All the synthesized compounds have been screened for their antibacterial activity and are found to exhibit significant activity.

Keywords : Cycloaddition reaction, novel isoxazolines, diastereoselectivity, MWI, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Nitrones are effective 1,3-dipoles and can undergo readily cycloaddition reaction with various olefins and alkynes to produce substituted isoxazolidines and isoxazolines¹. Moreover, nitrones can be used as potential oxidizing reagents in the conversion of various alkyl halides to aldehydes and ketones with atom efficiency²⁻⁴. They are also versatile intermediates for the synthesis of natural products and many biologically interesting molecules⁵. Owing to the labile nature of the N–O bond under mild reducing conditions, isoxazolines provide easy access to a variety of fascinating 1,3-difunctional amino alcohols⁶. The use of microwaves in organic synthesis has increased dramatically within the past decade, receiving widespread acceptance and becoming an indispensable tool⁷. Microwave technology has become a powerful tool in organic synthesis, since by employing this technique it is generally possible to prepare organic compounds very fast with high purity and better yields compared to other more conventional methods⁵. Moreover, the technique is considered as an important approach towards 'Green Chemistry' because of its eco-friendly nature. Microwave irradiation can be used as a facile and general method for the construction of variety of isoxazolidine and isoxazoline derivatives where considerably shortened reaction time is

involved⁷. In continuation of our green methodological synthesis using α -amino and α -chloro nitrones in solid phase and in hydrated media⁸⁻¹¹, we report herein diastereoselective synthesis of some novel isoxazoline derivatives using *N*-methyl- α -chloro nitron⁸ with different alkynes with excellent yield (Scheme 1; Table 1) under microwave irradiation.

Furthermore, synthetic potential of the novel isoxazoline derivatives (2-4) are tremendous as they could be converted into 1,3 difunctional amino alcohols (Scheme 2). Initial reports have been already reported and detailed studies are in progress^{6b}.

Results and discussion

The general mechanism for the development of nitron 1 from chlorohydrin (R = Ph) has been already reported⁸ and we have followed the same pathway in the present study. The reaction of nitron 1 with various alkynes follow the general mechanism pattern of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions as found in literature^{5,6a}. For the present study, we have chosen highly electron deficient alkynes like dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate, phenyl methyl propiolate and acetylene dicarboxylic acid (but-2-ynedioic acid) respectively to study the diastereoselectivity in these cycloaddition reactions. Excellent diastereofacial

(iii) Reaction condition : MWI, nitron 1 (1 mmol), dipolarophile (1 equivalent), dry DMF, 5–7 min

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physicochemical data of synthesized novel isoxazoline derivatives (2-4)

Entry	Nitron	Dipolarophile ^a	Time (min)	Cycloadduct ^b	Product ratio (%)	Yield ^c (%)
1	<i>N</i> -Methyl- α -chloro nitron (1)	Phenyl methyl propiolate	5	2a : Yellow gummy liquid 2b : Yellow liquid	2a : 64 (48) 2b : 33 (26)	97 (74)
2	<i>N</i> -Methyl- α -chloro nitron (1)	Dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate	5	3a : Red viscous liquid 3b : Dark red liquid	3a : 62 (40) 3b : 33 (28)	95 (68)
3	<i>N</i> -Methyl- α -chloro nitron (1)	Acetylene dicarboxylic acid	6	4a : Colourless liquid 4b : Colourless liquid	4a : 65 (43) 4b : 30 (21)	95 (64)

^aReaction condition : Nitron 1 (1 mmol), dipolarophile (1 equivalent), dry DMF, MWI.

^bAll the compounds were characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, MS, HRMS spectral data.

^cIsolated yields after purification. Figures in parenthesis indicate reactions performed in conventional methods.

Scheme 2

selectivity has been observed in the reported nitron cycloaddition reactions described here with alkynes. A new approach of synthesis of *N*-methyl- α -chloro nitron (1) from dihydropyran via chlorohydrin has been already reported⁸. The addition of nitron (1) to alkynes result mixture of diastereoisomer **2a-4a** and **2b-4b** (Scheme 1; Table 1) in almost 65 : 35 ratio in all cases). These results can be rationalized by an *exo* approach of the nitron for the major cycloadducts (**2a-4a**) which has the *Z* configuration (transition state 1)¹². The minor cycloadducts (**2b-4b**) are formed by the *endo* approach of *Z* nitron (transition state 2)¹³.

Most relevant are the coupling constants ($J_{H_3, CHCl}$) of the diastereoisomers. For **2a-4a**, this coupling constant is almost 6.24 to 6.16 Hz, implying a *cis* relationship between H_3 and $CHCl$ protons whereas **2b-4b** has a coupling constant of 2.56 to 2.44 Hz which implies a *trans* relationship between H_3 and $CHCl$ protons¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Comparing the ¹H NMR spectrum of **2a-4a** and **2b-4b**, we suggest the major and minor conformers of novel isoxazoline ring systems for **2a-4a** and **2b-4b**. (Fig. 1).

All the cycloadducts are stable and have prominent molecular ion peak and base peaks in the mass spectrum as expected. Like other isoxazoline derivatives reported in the literature¹⁷, we have also obtained expected fragmentation peaks due to the development of different

$R_1 = Me$; $R_1 = Ph$, $R_2 = COOCH_3$; $R_1 = R_2 = COOCH_3$;
 $R_1 = R_2 = COOH$; $R_3 = -CHCl(CH_2)_3OH$

Fig. 1

aziridine derivatives. Base peaks are obtained due to loss of $PhCO$ for phenyl methyl propiolate, $COOCH_3$ for dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate and $COOH$ for acetylene dicarboxylic acid cycloadducts respectively. Hence it is confirmed that during mass fragmentation, the cycloadducts underwent rearrangement to aziridine derivatives. The detailed mass fragmentation pattern is shown in Scheme 3. All the isoxazoline derivatives (**2-4**) showed $M^+ + 2$ peak values of characteristic relative heights in the mass spectrum and it is due to isotopic abundance of Cl^{37} atoms in these derivatives.

Antibacterial screening test :

All the synthesized isoxazoline derivatives (**2-4**) were subjected to *in vitro* screening against *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Vibrio cholerae*. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined using cup plate assay method according to the standard procedure¹⁸. Nutrient agar was used as a culture medium. At first strains of desired bacteria were isolated and were suspended in normal saline. From each bacterial suspension 0.1 mL was taken with the help of pipette and was spread on preprepared nutrient agar plate, with the help of spreader. Then cups were scooped out

Scheme 3. Development of aziridine derivatives

from each plate with the help of a cork borer and then to the respective cups different derivatives of the isoxazoline (2-4) of concentrations (1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 600, 400, 200, 100, 50, 25, 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) were added. The plates were incubated at 34 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h and then results were recorded. The lowest concentration, which showed no visible growth, was taken as an end point minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). All the compounds showed MIC 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ except 4b which showed MIC 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Proteus vulgaris*. It has been observed that the derivatives of isoxazolines (2-4) have good antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive (*S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli* and *S. flexneri*) bacteria, hence it can be concluded that the derivatives used were broad spectrum antibiotics¹⁸. The MIC value ob-

tained for isoxazoline derivatives ranges from 10–50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ very close to the MIC values of most commonly used antibiotics like Penicillin (10 units), Sulphonamide (300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), Nalidixic acid (512 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) etc. and hence they are equally effective and can be prescribed after testing of LD_{50} ^{19,20}.

Experimental

^1H NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker DRX 300 spectrometer (300 MHz, FT NMR) using TMS as internal standard. ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on the same instrument at 75 MHz. The coupling constants (J) are given in Hz. IR spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer RX 1-881 machine as film or as KBr pellets for all the products. MS spectra were recorded with a

Jeol SX-102 (FAB) instrument. The HRMS spectra were recorded on a DART-HRMS, JMS-T100LC, Accu-TOF instrument. All the reactions were monitored by TLC using 0.25 mm silica gel plates (Merck 60F₂₅₄ UV indicator) while column chromatography was performed with silica gel (E. Merck, India) 60–200 mesh. All other reagents and solvents were purified after receiving from commercial suppliers. *N*-Methylhydroxylamine was purchased from Aldrich Chemical Company and was used as received. Microwave irradiations were carried out using microwave oven KENSTER 19LKH, 19SSLM at 2450 MHz.

General procedure of cycloaddition for diastereomeric isoxazolines (conventional) :

In a 100 mL conical flask, nitrone **1** (1 mmol) and phenyl methyl propiolate (1 equivalent) were added to 25 mL dry ether and stirred at room temperature with a magnetic stirrer under N₂ atmosphere for 26 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC (*R*_f = 0.52, 0.64). After completion of the reaction, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure using a vacuum pump and the mixture of diastereoisomers were purified and separated by column chromatography using ethyl acetate-hexane to furnish yellow liquids. **2a** : 48%; **2b** : 26% (Scheme 1). This procedure was tested for other substrates listed in Table 1. But due to poor yield and slow reaction rates this methodology was not considered.

General procedure of cycloaddition for diastereomeric isoxazolines (MWI) :

A mixture of nitrone **1** (1 mmol) and phenyl methyl propiolate (1 equivalent) in dry DMF (5 drops) was taken in a 25 ml Erlenmeyer flask and subjected to microwave irradiation at medium power (50%) for 5 min (entry 1). The completion of reaction was monitored by TLC (*R*_f = 0.56; 0.64). The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into crushed ice. The reaction mass was extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layer was washed with brine, dried over anhydrous MgSO₄, filtered and concentrated under vacuum to obtain the crude products. Pure products (**2a**, **2b**) were obtained by column chromatography over silica gel using ethyl acetate and hexane (entry 1, Table 1, Scheme 1). This procedure was followed for the reaction of nitrone **1** with dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate and acetylene dicarboxylic acids listed in Table 1.

(S)-Methyl-3-((*S*)-1-chloro-4-hydroxybutyl)-2,3-dihydro-2-methyl-5-phenylisoxazole-4-carboxylate (**2a**) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3630–3575 (br), 3050 (m), 2960 (s), 1750 (s), 1470 (m), 1300 (m), 776 (s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.94–6.78 (5H, m, C₆H₅ hydrogens), 5.05–4.97 (1H, br, -CH₂OH, exchangeable in D₂O), 3.95 (1H, d, *J* 6.22 Hz, C₃H), 3.58 (1H, dt, *J* 6.16, 6.18 Hz, CHCl), 3.23 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 2.44 (3H, s, -COOCH₃), 1.68–1.32 (6H, m, CH₂ protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 172.66 (carbonyl carbon), 134.12, 132.76, 130.54, 128.25 (aromatic carbons), 94.28 (CHCl), 84.16 (C₅), 73.44 (C₃), 52.92 (C₄), 43.35 (-COOCH₃), 36.82 (N-Me), 28.67, 25.70, 26.34 (3CH₂ carbons); FAB-MS : *m/z* 327 (M⁺+2), 325 (M⁺), 248, 220, 205, 189, 105, 77; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₀O₄NCl (M), 325.1300, Found : M⁺, 325.1286.

(R)-Methyl-3-((*S*)-1-chloro-4-hydroxybutyl)-2,3-dihydro-2-methyl-5-phenylisoxazole-4-carboxylate (**2b**) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3645–3570 (br), 3055 (m), 2950 (s), 1755 (s), 1470 (m), 1310 (m), 772 (s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.04–6.95 (5H, m, C₆H₅ hydrogens), 5.00–4.93 (1H, br, -CH₂OH, exchangeable in D₂O), 3.78 (1H, d, *J* 3.22 Hz, C₃H), 3.54 (1H, dt, *J* 2.74, 2.50 Hz, CHCl), 3.27 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 2.28 (3H, s, -COOCH₃), 1.83–1.56 (6H, m, CH₂ protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 170.70 (carbonyl carbon), 132.08, 130.23, 128.12, 127.29 (aromatic carbons), 90.63 (CHCl), 81.74 (C₅), 75.47 (C₃), 55.40 (C₄), 42.06 (-COOCH₃), 37.36 (N-Me), 29.21, 27.64, 25.26 (3CH₂ carbons); FAB-MS : *m/z* 327 (M⁺+2), 325 (M⁺), 248, 220, 205, 189, 113, 105, 77; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₀O₄NCl (M), 325.1300, Found : M⁺, 325.1281.

(S)-Dimethyl-3-((*S*)-1-chloro-4-hydroxybutyl)-2,3-dihydro-2-methylisoxazole-4,5-dicarboxylate (**3a**) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3585–3466 (br), 2850 (s), 1752 (s), 1660 (m), 1440 (s), 1260 (m) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 5.13–5.05 (1H, br, OH, exchanged in D₂O), 4.64 (1H, d, *J* 6.28 Hz, C₃H), 4.24 (dt, *J* 6.06, 6.20 Hz, CHCl), 3.30 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 2.24 (3H, s, -COOCH₃), 2.28 (3H, s, -COOCH₃), 2.05–1.48 (6H, m, CH₂ protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 168.24, 167.48 (carbonyl carbons), 93.57 (CHCl), 88.62 (C₅), 72.92 (C₃), 58.40 (C₄), 42.52, 41.68 (ester carbons), 35.03 (N-Me), 32.17, 30.23, 28.80 (3CH₂ carbons); FAB-MS : *m/z* 309 (M⁺+2), 307 (M⁺), 276,

248, 220, 200, 189, 107, 87, 59, 31; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{18}O_6NCl$ (M), 307.1080, Found : M^+ , 307.1058.

(*R*)-Dimethyl-3-(1-chloro-4-hydroxybutyl)-2,3-dihydro-2-methylisoxazole-4,5-dicarboxylate (**3b**) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3580–3465 (br), 2860 (s), 1754 (s), 1660 (m), 1435 (s), 1264 (m) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 5.10–5.02 (1H, br, OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.57 (1H, d, J 2.28 Hz, C_3H), 4.35 (dt, J 2.06, 2.20 Hz, $CHCl$), 3.33 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 2.50 (3H, s, $-COOCH_3$), 2.46 (3H, s, $-COOCH_3$), 1.95–1.43 (6H, m, CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 168.85, 168.13 (carbonyl carbons), 91.24 ($CHCl$), 86.90 (C_5), 73.66 (C_3), 57.77 (C_4), 43.00, 41.81 (ester carbons), 34.72 (N-Me), 30.22, 28.20, 27.16 ($3CH_2$ carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 309 ($M^+ + 2$), 307 (M^+), 276, 248, 220, 205, 189, 113, 107, 87, 59, 31; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{18}O_6NCl$ (M), 307.1080, Found : M^+ , 307.1063.

(*S*)-3-((*S*)-1-Chloro-4-hydroxybutyl)-2,3-dihydro-2-methylisoxazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid (**4a**) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3590–3485 (br), 2950 (s), 1725 (m), 1666 (s), 1450 (m), 1310 (m) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 10.24 (1H, s, COOH), 10.16 (1H, s, COOH), 5.16–5.08 (1H, br, OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.82 (1H, d, J 6.26 Hz, C_3H), 3.50 (1H, dt, J 6.16, 6.12 Hz, $CHCl$), 3.31 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 1.75–1.36 (6H, m, CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 173.69, 172.04 (carboxyl carbons), 90.50 ($CHCl$), 86.53 (C_5), 79.28 (C_3), 55.40 (C_4), 36.44 (N-Me), 28.05, 26.50, 24.78 ($3CH_2$ carbons); MS : m/z 281 ($M^+ + 2$), 279 (M^+), 234, 206, 191, 99, 107, 73, 45; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{14}O_6NCl$ (M), 279.0820, Found : M^+ , 279.0807.

(*R*)-3-(1-Chloro-4-hydroxybutyl)-2,3-dihydro-2-methylisoxazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid (**4b**) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3596–3482 (br), 2955 (s), 1720 (m), 1660 (s), 1454 (m), 1300 (m) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 10.20 (1H, s, COOH), 10.12 (1H, s, COOH), 5.10–5.03 (1H, br, OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.76 (1H, d, J 2.48 Hz, C_3H), 3.60 (1H, dt, J 2.45, 2.22 Hz, $CHCl$), 3.34 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 1.60–1.27 (6H, m, CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 172.05, 171.14 (carboxyl carbons), 93.10 ($CHCl$), 85.70 (C_5), 77.23 (C_3), 54.37 (C_4), 35.13 (N-Me), 26.78, 24.62, 24.18 ($3CH_2$ carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 281 ($M^+ + 2$), 279 (M^+), 234, 206, 191, 99,

107, 73, 45 ; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{14}O_6NCl$ (M), 279.0820, Found : M^+ , 279.0802.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have demonstrated a convenient, inexpensive and highly efficient protocol for the synthesis of isoxazoline derivatives using *N*-methyl- α -chloro nitrene in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction under microwave irradiation. The notable factors of this methodology are : (a) excellent purity and high yields, (b) short reaction times and (c) operational simplicity and non-toxicity of the reactant, reagents used. Therefore, it is believed that procedure described here will find important applications in the environment friendly synthesis of isoxazoline derivatives and thereby offering greater scope in cycloaddition reactions.

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